

Strengthening Self-Efficiency, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Ocb) And Empowerment In Efforts To Increase Teacher Innovativeness: Empire On State School Teachers In Bogor City

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
April, 2021

Accepted:
July, 2021

Keywords :

Innovativeness, Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Empowerment

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5093915

Abstract

This study aims to increase the innovativeness of public elementary school teachers in Bogor City through efforts to develop self-efficacy variables, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and empowerment by identifying the strengths of the relationship between these variables. The population in this study were all PNS teachers in "A" accredited State Elementary Schools in the City of Bogor with a total of 1648 teachers spread over 158 Public Elementary Schools in 6 (six) sub-districts throughout the City of Bogor. Sampling using multistage proportional random sampling and the calculation of the number of samples using the Taro Yamane formula, obtained a research sample of 270 people. This study uses the correlational method to test the research hypothesis, namely to find out whether there is a positive relationship between self-efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and empowerment with innovativeness. Based on these results analysis is then carried out to determine recommendations and determine the priority order for handling indicators that must be improved. The results of the quantitative research show that: There is a positive and significant relationship between Self-Efficacy and Innovativeness, the r_{y1} correlation value is 0.148 with very weak criteria; There is a positive and significant relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Innovativeness, the r_{y2} correlation value is 0.599 with strong criteria, and there is a positive and significant relationship between Empowerment and Innovativeness, the r_{y3} correlation value is 0.713, which means the relationship is very strong. The results of the analysis show that innovativeness can be increased through increasing self-efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior and empowerment. The results of the analysis also show that the components of innovation, self-efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior and empowerment that need improvement are 1) Sportsmanship; 2) Magnitude; 3) Generality; 4) Courtesy; 5) Altruism; 6) Communications; 7) Process Innovation; 8) Conscientiousness; 9) Confident; 10) Product Innovation; 11) Desire; 12) Accountability; 13) Trusts; 14) Strength, and 15) Credibility. While the components that need to be maintained are Service Innovation and Civic Virtue. There are indicators that will be the subject of discussion in an Action Plan as a follow-up to the research that has been done, namely for indicators of Sportsmanship, Courtesy, Altruism, Conscientiousness, Communication, Confident, Desire, Trust, and Credibility.

Introduction

Education is an invaluable producer of long-term human resources for the survival of human civilization. So it is not surprising that education has become a priority in almost all countries considering education as something important and a top priority in the context of nation building. Teachers in the context of education have a very large and important role in creating the next generation of a superior nation. The teacher plays a role as one part of the main component in education. It is the teacher who is at the forefront of the process of implementing educational activities. It is also the teacher who deals directly with students to transfer knowledge and at the same time serves as an educator by applying positive values through the guidance and example of a teacher. Facing the changing era of globalization which is very fast. Demanding teachers to develop and teachers have a heavy duty and mission. It is proper for teachers to have innovations in carrying out their duties as educators. Innovations made by a teacher in carrying out learning activities greatly affect the quality of learning outcomes received by students. Innovative teachers will make new breakthroughs in improving the quality of student learning outcomes. Such as creating or creating new strategies in carrying out their duties. This can be done

through certain media that are tailored to the needs, or through the use of technological sophistication, so that it can help facilitate the work and duties of a teacher as an educator. Learning activities will be carried out in an interesting and not boring way for students. This makes learning objectives can be carried out efficiently.

Based on the understandings of the background problems described above, it can be understood how important efforts to increase teacher innovation are in order to shape the dynamics of a better school organizational life. From some of the descriptions presented in the background, the following problems can be identified: 1. Lack of achievement motivation with encouragement from within each individual to achieve the best results will produce innovative teachers. 2. Emotional intelligence that has not yet been formed in a teacher, so that it affects teacher innovation, the more stable a teacher's emotions, the more innovative. The application of the principal's leadership that has not been effective can affect the innovativeness of teachers. Principals who provide encouragement and inspiration to teachers will encourage teachers to dare to make innovations. 4. Organizational culture that is not yet conducive can affect innovative teachers. Schools that already have a good, systematic and organized organizational culture will create situations and conditions that motivate teachers to innovate. The lack of achievement of the level of teacher welfare causes the low motivation of teachers to innovate. Guaranteed living needs of teachers through various welfare benefits will increase teacher motivation in innovating. 6. Lack of work discipline for teachers can result in low work performance, so it is suspected that it can affect teacher innovation. 7. Lack of leadership communication with teachers can affect the willingness and ability of teachers to work, so it is suspected that it can affect teacher innovation. Self-efficacy in teachers is something that affects the success of teaching in schools. Teachers who have low self-efficacy will feel doubtful about their abilities, reduce their efforts in achieving goals, even give up so that it affects teacher innovation. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of teachers towards organizations that are suspected of having an influence on the willingness of teachers to work, so that it is suspected that it will affect teacher innovation. 10. Empowerment that does not support and facilitate teacher activities and work results in a decrease in teacher participation, so that it is suspected that it can affect teacher innovation.

In general, this study aims to increase the innovativeness of public elementary school teachers in the city of Bogor through efforts to develop self-efficacy variables, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and empowerment by identifying the strengths of the relationship between these variables, as follows 1. The strength of the relationship between self-efficacy with teacher innovation. 2. Strength of the relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and teacher innovativeness. 3. The strength of the relationship between empowerment and teacher innovation. 4. The strength of the relationship between self-efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior together with teacher innovation. 5. The strength of the relationship between self-efficacy and empowerment together with teacher innovation. 6. The strength of the relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and empowerment together with teacher innovation. 7. The strength of the relationship between self-efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and empowerment together with teacher innovation.

Method

This research is a quantitative research with survey method, so that more comprehensive, valid, reliable, and objective data will be obtained. Survey method with correlational approach. Information on survey results was collected from respondents using a questionnaire for all variables, both Teacher Innovativeness (Y), Self-Efficacy (X1), Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X2), and Empowerment (X3). The relationship between each independent variable and the dependent variable is presented in the problem constellation as shown in Figure 1 below

Population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities or characteristics that are determined by a researcher to be studied and then draw conclusions. The population in this study were all PNS teachers in "A" accredited State Elementary Schools in the City of Bogor with a total of 1648 teachers spread over 158 Public Elementary Schools in 6 (six) sub-districts throughout the City of Bogor. Based on the above calculation with an error rate of 0.05% from 826 SDN teachers in Bogor City, 270 people will be sampled. Data processing in this study used descriptive analysis techniques and inferential analysis with a correlational approach. In this data analysis sequentially discusses the normality test, homogeneity test, linearity test, and correlation. Qualitative data is collected after quantitative data is obtained. The collection of qualitative data is collected through interviews and documentation studies, such as learning programs, photos, and others related to the implementation of inclusive education. Interview guidelines are seen from the results of the inclusive index obtained. The results of the inclusive index obtained are relatively low, so the researcher will conduct interviews with related parties, such as teachers, principals, or students. After qualitative data obtained through interviews, then the qualitative data is reduced. Data reduction is the activity of summarizing or

selecting the main things and important things from the data needed according to the facts of the problem. Then after the data is reduced, then the data is coded or given a symbol. Descriptive analysis was carried out to find the standard deviation, frequency distribution, mode, mean, median and histogram of the scores obtained on the variables of Teacher Innovativeness, Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Empowerment. The data analysis technique used in this study was to use steps -Steps as proposed by Sugiyono (2007: 271), namely as follows: Data Collection (Data Collection) Data collection is an integral part of data analysis activities. Data collection activities in this study were using interviews and documentation studies. Data Reduction Data reduction is defined as the process of selecting, focusing on simplification and transformation of rough data that emerges from written notes in the field. Reduction is carried out since data collection begins by making summaries, coding, tracing themes, making clusters, writing memos and so on with the aim of eliminating irrelevant data/information. Data Displays. Display data is a description of a set of structured information that provides the possibility of drawing conclusions and taking action. The presentation of qualitative data is presented in the form of narrative text. The presentation can also be in the form of matrices, diagrams, tables and charts.

Inferential analysis in this study is used with the aim that the research results can be concluded to be generalized from the hypothesis testing that has been formulated. Prior to the correlation analysis, the hypothesis analysis requirements test was carried out, using normality, homogeneity and regression analysis tests. The correlation test was used to examine the relationship between the variables of Self-Efficacy (X_1) and Teacher Innovativeness (Y), Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X_2) and Teacher Innovativeness (Y), and Empowerment (X_3) and Teacher Innovativeness (Y) using a simple correlation equation. To examine the relationship between Self-Efficacy (X_1) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X_2) together with Teacher Innovativeness (Y), the relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X_2) and Empowerment (X_3) together with Teacher Innovativeness (Y), the relationship between Self-Efficacy (X_1) and Empowerment (X_3) together with Teacher Innovativeness (Y), and the relationship between Self-Efficacy (X_1), Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X_2), and Empowerment (X_3) together with Teacher Innovativeness (Y) uses multiple correlation equations. The next step, a determination test is carried out with the aim of knowing how big the contribution of each independent variable is Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Empowerment with the dependent variable of Teacher Innovativeness either individually or together.

Fig 1. Research Model

The alternative hypotheses in this study are as follows:

H1: There is a positive relationship between Self-Efficacy and Teacher Innovativeness.

H2: There is a positive relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Teacher Innovativeness.

H3: There is a positive relationship between Empowerment and Teacher Innovativeness

H4: There is a positive relationship between Self-Efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior together with Teacher Innovativeness.

H5: There is a positive relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment together with Teacher Innovativeness.

H6: There is a positive relationship between Self-Efficacy and Empowerment together with Teacher Innovativeness.

H7: There is a positive relationship between Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Empowerment together with Teacher Innovativeness.

Result and Discussion

The description of the results of this study begins with the results of descriptive statistical analysis to describe the data for each variable, followed by the results of prerequisite tests to determine the validity of using parametric statistics in hypothesis testing and inferential results to test hypotheses. The data was obtained by measuring the variables of innovation, self-efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior and empowerment based on the responses of respondents to the instrument items of these variables. The data was collected from a sample of 270 elementary school teachers in the city of Bogor. The sample used in this study was 270 respondents. The maximum score for the innovation variable is 155 and the minimum score is 86 with a range of 69. The average variable for innovation is 127.33 units with a standard deviation of 9.80 units from the number of respondents totaling 270. With a standard deviation of 9.80 units, it means that if it is connected with an average PNS teacher innovativeness of 127.33 units/person, the innovativeness of PNS teachers at State Elementary Schools in Bogor City will range from 127.33 to 9.80 units.

Table 1. Hypothesis Testing

Correlation	Regresion	SigRegretion			Conclusion
		f_{hitung}	$f_{tabel}^{*)}$ 0,05	$f_{tabel}^{*)}$ 0,01	
Y-X ₁	$\hat{Y}=129,380+0,017X_1$	13,148	3,89	6,76	Very significant and can be used to predict innovation based on self-efficacy values
Y-X ₂	$\hat{Y}=83,657+0,362X_2$	39,776	3,89	6,76	Very significant and can be used to predict innovation based on the value of Organizational Citizenship Behavior
Y-X ₃	$\hat{Y}=80,571+0,380X_3$	93,760	3,89	6,76	Significant and can be used to predict innovation based on the value of empowerment
Y-X ₁ X ₂	$\hat{Y}=91,776+0,246X_1+0,541X_2$	33,459	3,04	4,71	Very significant and can be used to predict innovation based on self-efficacy values and Organizational Citizenship Behavior
Y-X ₁ X ₃	$\hat{Y}=83,131+0,021X_1+0,380X_3$	46,895	3,04	4,71	Very significant and can be used to predict innovation based on the value of self-efficacy and empowerment
Y-X ₂ X ₃	$\hat{Y}=58,159+0,236X_2+0,331X_3$	59,923	3,04	4,71	It is very significant and can be used to predict innovation based on the values of Organizational Citizenship Behavior and empowerment
Y-X ₁ X ₂ X ₃	$\hat{Y}=66,260+0,181X_1+0,378X_2+0,303X_3$	47,091	2,65	3,88	Very significant and can be used to predict innovation based on the value of self-efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior and empowerment

From the results of processing and calculating research data, it is known that the hypotheses proposed in this study are all accepted, where the relationship that occurs between the research variables both partially and simultaneously is positive and very significant.

1. The Relationship between Strengthening Self-Efficacy and Increasing Innovativeness

From the results of the first hypothesis test, it was concluded that the relationship between Self-Efficacy and Innovativeness was very significant positive, indicated by the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($22,708 > 1,97$) at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The resulting correlation equation is $\hat{Y} = 129.380 + 0.017X_1$, which means that every increase in one level of Self-Efficacy will result in an increase in Innovativeness of 0.017 at a constant of 129.380. The strength of the relationship between Self-Efficacy and Innovativeness obtained a correlation value of r_{y1} of 0.148 which means the relationship is very weak and positive, so it can be said that the better the Self-Efficacy, the better the Innovativeness, and vice versa if the lower the Self-Efficacy, the Innovativeness becomes not good. The contribution of Self-Efficacy to Innovativeness is obtained by the Coefficient of Determination (KD) value of

0.022%, where this value means that 2.2% of Innovativeness is influenced by Self-Efficacy and 97.8% of Innovativeness is influenced by other variables. Another study that supports the results of this study is the research conducted by Jen-Chia Chang (2011: 33) entitled "The Impact of Self-efficacy on Innovative Work Behavior for Teachers self-efficacy" which resulted in the finding that self-efficacy has a strong and significant relationship with innovativeness ($r = 0.73$ $p < 0.001$). Thus, increasing self-efficacy is predicted to increase teacher innovativeness. Bien et al. (2014: 342) states that innovation is in the process of creating new ideas and putting them into practice. Here we will examine it as a product (product innovation) from process innovation. (Innovation is the activity of creating new ideas and putting them into practice. Here we will examine them as a product (product innovation) of process innovation). An indicator that can measure innovation is process innovation (process innovation) is an action and/or result of the development of the use/mobilization of knowledge, skills and product innovation (product innovation) an activity that seeks to provide solutions to existing problems. According to Aslam (2018: 233) stated that Self-efficacy forecast the events and actions interrelated through Knowledge sharing similar exchange the knowledge and translating the feedback of performance. Self-efficacy likewise affects in significant as well as positive way to Knowledge sharing Behavior. Workers with more prominent measures of Self-efficacy will likely take part more in knowledge sharing exercises. (Self-efficacy predicts interrelated events and actions through sharing the same knowledge, exchanging knowledge and translating performance feedback. Self-efficacy also influences significantly and positively for knowledge-sharing behavior. Workers with more prominent levels of self-efficacy are likely to participate more much in the practice of sharing knowledge.

2. The Relationship between Strengthening Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Increasing Innovativeness

From the results of the second hypothesis test, it was concluded that the relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Innovativeness was very significant positive, which was indicated by the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($12,043 > 1,97$) at level = 0,05. The resulting correlation equation is , which means that every increase of one level of Organizational Citizenship Behavior will result in an increase in Innovativeness of 0.362 at a constant of 83,657. The strength of the relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Innovativeness obtained a correlation value of r^2 of 0.599 which means the relationship is moderate and positive, so it can be said that the better the Organizational Citizenship Behavior, the better the Innovativeness and vice versa if the less good the Organizational Citizenship Behavior, the Innovativeness becomes not good. The contribution made by Organizational Citizenship Behavior to Innovativeness is the Coefficient of Determination (KD) value of 0.359 with weak criteria, where this value means that 35.9% of Innovativeness is influenced by Organizational Citizenship Behavior and 64.1% of Innovativeness is influenced by other variables.

Other research results that support this research are Judipat N Obiora's research (2015: 6) entitled "Opportunity For Innovation And Organizational Citizenship Behavior In The Nigerian Hospitality Industry" which results in the finding that Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a moderate and significant relationship with innovation ($r = 0.555$ $p < 0.001$). Thus the increase in Organizational Citizenship Behavior is predicted to increase teacher innovation. Schumpeter (2014: 327) states that innovation is an attempt to create and implement something into a combination so that, with innovation one can add value from products, services, work processes, and policies not only to educational institutions but also to stakeholders and communities . (Innovation is an effort to create and implement something into a combination so that, with innovation one can add value to products, services, work processes, and policies not only for educational institutions but also stakeholders and society). The indicators of innovation are: a. Product Innovation. Is something that can be seen as a product's functional progress that can take the product one step further compared to competing products; b. Service Innovation. Focus on making changes to the product line in order to attract more attention from consumers; c. Process Innovation. New ways of working in producing a service or product, and d. Policy Innovation. Efforts to take a new step in making a regulation that is flexible. Podsakoff et al. (2010: 513-563) states that Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) as discretionary individual Behavior, which is not directly and explicitly rewarded by a formal reward system, and which overall encourages the effectiveness of Organizational functions. It is free and voluntary, since such conduct is not required by role requirements or job descriptions that are clearly required under contract with the Organizational; but as a personal choice. (Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) as individual behavior that is free (discretionary), which is not directly and explicitly rewarded by the formal reward system, and which as a whole encourages the effectiveness of organizational functions. It is free and voluntary, because the behavior is not required by role requirements or job descriptions that are expressly required by contract with the organization; rather as a personal choice). Indicators of Organizational Citizenship Behavior are: a. Altruism, which is concerned with the interests of others such as immediate behavior towards others; b. Conscientiousness, namely being careful or listening to your heart; c. Sportsmanship, or sportsmanship such as tolerance for discomfort at work that cannot be avoided without complaint; d. Courtesy,

or politeness such as telling others in preventing incidents at work that cause a problem, and e. Civic virtue, namely the goodness of citizens or citizens of the organization.

3. The Relationship between Strengthening Empowerment and Innovativeness

From the results of the third hypothesis test, it was concluded that the relationship between Empowerment and Innovativeness was very significant positive, which was indicated by the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($16.592 > 1.97$) at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The resulting correlation equation is $r = 0.713$, which means that every increase in one level of Empowerment will result in an increase in Innovativeness of 0.380 at a constant of 80.571. The strength of the relationship between Empowerment and Innovativeness obtained r^2 correlation value of 0.509 which means the relationship is strong and positive, so it can be said that the better the Empowerment, the better the Innovativeness will be and vice versa if the Empowerment is not good, the Innovativeness is not good. The contribution of Empowerment to Innovativeness is obtained by the Coefficient of Determination (KD) value of 0.509 with moderate criteria, where this value means that 50.9% of Innovativeness is influenced by Empowerment and 49.1% of Innovativeness is influenced by other variables. Another research result that supports this research is Hasan Hüseyin Uzunbacak's (2015: 986) research entitled "The Impacts Of Employee Empowerment On Innovation: A Survey On Isparta And Burdur Organized Industrial Zones" which results in the finding that empowerment has a strong and significant relationship with innovation. ($r = 0.770$ $p < 0.000$). Thus the increase in empowerment is predicted to increase teacher innovation.

According to Uzunbacak (2015: 981) states that innovation, in its modern sense, has claimed its place within the literature as innovativeness and the word innovation, has its roots in the Latin word *innovare*. This word, which means "to change," "to differ," and "to renew," consists of *in* meaning "inside" and *novare* meaning "renew, new." Spreitzer (2005: 1442-1465) states that empowerment is a process whereby an individual has the power to participate directly to control and influence an event that has a direct effect on his or her life. (Empowerment as a process where individuals have the power to participate directly to control and influence an event that has a direct effect on their lives). The indicators of empowerment are: a. Work team and information sharing are building blocks (forming an open communication work team with workers); b. Provide the training and resources needed to do good jobs (development of skills and expertise is an important dimension in empowerment programs, because training is important to improve job skills and is an important part of employee empowerment); c. Provide measurement, feedback and reinforcement (to determine the improvement and progress made by employees, it is necessary to measure the effectiveness of the empowerment program), by providing a standard for measuring success that can be used as a work control tool on employee performance; d. On going reinforcement (management support by providing reinforcement) that will continuously support and motivate employees because every employee wants to be rewarded for the achievements he has achieved and supervisors need to give a good assessment and notify others of the achievements that have been achieved), and e. Provide reasonability and authority (granting sufficient authority and responsibility for the work to determine the actions required to complete the various assigned tasks). Flexible in internal procedure (creating more flexible rules and systems). Because the flexible rules will facilitate decision making and support organizations that are easy to adapt to environmental changes that occur so that the organization is more competitive than its competitors.

4. The Relationship between Self-Efficacy Strengthening and Organizational Citizenship Behavior Together with Innovativeness

From the results of the fourth hypothesis test, it is concluded that the relationship between Self-Efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior together with Innovativeness is a very significant positive which is indicated by the value of $F_{count} > F_{table}$ ($33.459 > 3.04$) at level $\alpha = 0.05$. The equation obtained is $r = 0.669$, this shows that an increase in one level of Self-Efficacy will result in an increase in Innovativeness of 0.246 at a constant 91.776, and each increase of one level of Organizational Citizenship Behavior will result in an increase in Innovativeness of 0.541 at a constant 91.776. The strength of the relationship between Self-Efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior together with Innovativeness obtained a correlation value of r^2 of 0.447 which means the relationship is strong and positive, so it can be said that the better Self-Efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior together, the better. Innovativeness is good and vice versa if the Self-Efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior are not good together, then Innovativeness is not good. The contribution of Self-Efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior to Innovativeness is obtained by the Coefficient of Determination (KD) value of 0.447 with moderate criteria, where this value means that 44.7% of Innovativeness is influenced by Self-Efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior and 55.3% of Innovativeness is influenced by other variables. The research results that support the results of this study are research conducted by Iqra Aslam (2018: 235) entitled "Does Self Efficacy Moderate the Relationship between innovation and Organizational Citizenship Behavior? (A quantitative Research in Civil Secretariat Quetta)" resulted in the finding that self-efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior had a strong and significant relationship with innovation ($r = 0.686$ $p < 0.000$). Thus, increasing self-efficacy and organizational citizenship

behavior is predicted to increase teacher innovation. Self-efficacy is an individual's belief that he or she is able to manage and decide the actions needed to carry out tasks well, with indicators: a. Magnitude refers to the individual's perception of a task that is considered difficult; b. Strength is related to the strength of one's self-efficacy when facing the demands of a task or a problem, and c. Generality refers to the level of confidence and ability to generalize tasks and previous experiences. Organizational Citizenship Behavior is the behavior of individuals in an organization that is voluntary, free and works beyond the core task and explicitly does not receive formal awards so that overall it is able to increase the effectiveness of organizational functions consisting of indicators: a. Behavior to help others (altruism); b. Behavior to prevent problems with coworkers (courtesy); c. Tolerance to less than ideal situations in the workplace (sportsmanship); d. Voluntary participation and support for organizational functions (civic virtue), and e. High dedication and dedication to work that exceeds the minimum requirements (conscientiousness). Innovation is an activity to create new ideas and put oneself in an improved service and service or improvement in achieving the services provided. The indicators of innovation: are a. Product innovation, namely activities that try to provide solutions to existing problems; b. Process innovation, namely the action and/or result of developing the use/mobilization of knowledge, skills, and c. Service innovation, i.e. focus on making changes to the product line in order to attract more attention from consumers. The findings obtained in this study identify that if the teacher has a high level of self-efficacy and good Organizational Citizenship Behavior, together these two variables contribute to increased innovativeness.

5. The Relationship between Self-Efficacy Strengthening and Empowerment Together with Innovativeness

From the results of the fifth hypothesis test, it was concluded that the relationship between Self-Efficacy and Empowerment together with Innovativeness was positive and very significant as indicated by the value of $F_{count} > F_{table}$ ($46.895 > 3.04$) at level $\alpha = 0.05$. The equation obtained is $y = 0.021x + 83.131$, this shows that an increase in one level of Self-Efficacy will result in an increase in Innovativeness of 0.021 at a constant of 83.131, and each increase of one level of Empowerment will result in an increase in Innovativeness of 0.380 at a constant of 83.131. The strength of the relationship between Self-Efficacy and Empowerment together with Innovativeness obtained a correlation value of $r_{1.3}$ of 0.714 which means the relationship is strong and positive, so it can be said that the better Self-Efficacy and Empowerment together, the better the Innovativeness and Empowerment together. On the other hand, if the Self-Efficacy and Empowerment are not good together, then Innovativeness becomes not good. The contribution of Self-Efficacy and Empowerment to Innovativeness is obtained by the Coefficient of Determination (KD) value of 0.509 with moderate criteria, where this value means that 50.9% of Innovativeness is influenced by Self-Efficacy and Empowerment and 49.1% of Innovativeness is influenced by variables other. The research results that support the results of this study are research conducted by Iqra Aslam (2018: 235) entitled "Does Self Efficacy Moderate the Relationship between innovation and Organizational Citizenship Behavior? (A quantitative Research in Civil Secretariat Quetta)" resulted in the finding that self-efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior have a strong and significant relationship with innovation ($r = 0.686$ $p < 0.000$). Thus, increasing self-efficacy is predicted to increase teacher innovation.

Self-efficacy is an individual's belief that he or she is able to manage and decide on the necessary actions to carry out tasks properly with the following indicators: a. Magnitude refers to the individual's perception of a task that is considered difficult; b. Strength is related to the strength of one's self-efficacy when facing the demands of a task or a problem, and c. Generality refers to the level of confidence and ability to generalize tasks and previous experiences. Empowerment is the behavior or action of giving or transferring some power, strength, or ability to individuals in the organization to become more empowered, which consists of indicators: a. Desire. The first stage in the empowerment model is the desire of management to delegate and involve workers; b. Trust. After the management wishes to empower, the next step is to build trust between management and employees. The existence of mutual trust between members of the organization will create good conditions for the exchange of information and advice without fear; c. Confidence is to create employee confidence by respecting the abilities possessed by employees; d. Credibility. Credibility with awards and developing a work environment that encourages healthy competition so as to create an organization that has high performance; e. Accountability is the accountability of employees to the given authority. By establishing consistently and clearly the roles, standards and objectives of evaluating employee performance, this stage serves as a means of evaluating employee performance in completion and responsibility for the given authority, and f. Communication is an open communication to create mutual understanding between employees and management. This openness can be realized by the existence of criticism and suggestions on the results and achievements of workers. Innovation is an activity to create new ideas and put oneself in an improved service and service or improvement in achieving the services provided. The indicators of innovation are: a. Product innovation, namely activities that try to provide solutions to existing problems; b. Process innovation, namely the action and/or result of developing the use/mobilization of knowledge, skills, and c. Service innovation, i.e. focus on making changes to the product line in order to attract more attention from consumers. The findings

obtained in this study identify that if the teacher has a high level of self-efficacy and good empowerment, together these two variables contribute to the increase in innovativeness.

6. Relationship between Strengthening Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment together with Innovativeness.

From the results of the sixth hypothesis test, it was concluded that the relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment together with Innovativeness was positive and very significant as indicated by the value of $F_{count} > F_{table}$ ($59.923 > 3.04$) at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The equation obtained is , this shows that an increase in one level of Organizational Citizenship Behavior will result in an increase in Innovativeness of 0.236 at a constant 58.159, and each increase in one level of Empowerment will result in an increase in Innovativeness of 0.331 at a constant 58.159. The strength of the relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment together with Innovativeness obtained a correlation value of r^2 of 0.746 which means the relationship is strong and positive, so it can be said that the better Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment together, the better it will be. Innovativeness and vice versa if the Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment are not good together, then Innovativeness becomes not good. The contribution made by Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment to Innovativeness is the Coefficient of Determination (KD) value of 0.556 with moderate criteria, where this value means that 55.6% of Innovativeness is influenced by Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment and 44.4% of Innovativeness is influenced by -other variables.

The results of the study that support the results of this study are the research conducted by Asli Goksoy (2017) entitled "The Role of Psychological Empowerment and Organizational Citizenship Behaviors on Innovation to Change" resulting in the finding that Organizational Citizenship Behavior and empowerment can affect innovation ($r = 0,93$ $p < 0.001$). Thus the increase in Organizational Citizenship Behavior and empowerment is predicted to increase teacher innovation. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is the behavior of individuals in an organization that is voluntary, free and works beyond the core task and explicitly does not receive formal awards so that overall it is able to increase the effectiveness of organizational functions, which consists of the following indicators: a. Behavior to help others (altruism); b. Behavior to prevent problems with coworkers (courtesy); c. Tolerance to less than ideal situations in the workplace (sportsmanship); d. Voluntary participation and support for organizational functions (civic virtue), and e. High dedication and dedication to work that exceeds the minimum requirements (conscientiousness). Empowerment is the behavior or act of giving or transferring some power, strength, or ability to individuals in the organization to become more empowered. Innovation is an activity to create new ideas and put oneself in an improved service and service or improvement in achieving the services provided. The indicators of innovation are: a. Product innovation, namely activities that try to provide solutions to existing problems; b. Process innovation, namely the action and/or result of developing the use/mobilization of knowledge, skills, and c. Service innovation, i.e. focus on making changes to the product line in order to attract more attention from consumers. The findings obtained in this study identify that if the teacher has a good level of Organizational Citizenship Behavior and empowerment, together these two variables contribute to increasing innovativeness.

7. Relationship between Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment with Innovativeness.

From the results of the seventh hypothesis test, it was concluded that the relationship between Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment together with Innovativeness was positive and very significant, indicated by the value of $F_{count} > F_{table}$ ($47.091 > 2.65$) at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The equation obtained is , this shows that an increase in one level of Self-Efficacy will result in an increase in innovativeness of 0.181 at a constant 66.260, an increase in one level of Organizational Citizenship Behavior will result in an increase in Innovativeness of 0.378 at a constant 66.260, and each increase in one level of Empowerment will result in an increase in Innovativeness. 0.303 at the constant 66.260. The strength of the relationship between Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Empowerment together with Innovativeness obtained a correlation value of r^2 of 0.767 which means the relationship is strong and positive, so it can be said that the better Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Empowerment together At the same time, the Innovativeness will be better and vice versa if the Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Empowerment are not good together, then Innovativeness is not good.

The contribution of Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Empowerment to Innovativeness is obtained by the Coefficient of Determination (KD) value of 0.588 with moderate criteria, where this value means that 58.8% of Innovativeness is influenced by Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Empowerment and is equal to 41.2% Innovativeness is influenced by other variables not examined in this study such as achievement motivation, emotional intelligence, leadership, organizational culture, welfare, work discipline, communication, and work creativity.

The research results that support the results of this study are research conducted by MohTaoefik. (2017: 71) entitled "Emotional Intelligence Mediation Effect on the Effect of Collaborative Supervision and Leadership on Teacher Innovative Behavior", stated that the innovative behavior of teachers can be influenced by the emotional condition of the strength part with a value of $= 0.686$ and a p-value of < 0.001 . Thus, increasing self-efficacy is predicted to increase teacher innovation. AriefAnshari (2018:221) entitled The Influence of Leader Member Exchange (LMX) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) on Innovative Work Behavior (IWB) To Improve Organizational Performance (Study At PT. (Persero) Angkasa Pura I Hasanuddin International Airport) resulted in the finding that OCB has an effect on innovation is $0.459 > 0.001$. Thus the increase in Organizational Citizenship Behavior is predicted to increase teacher innovation. Garcia and Calantone (2002: 110-132) state that innovation is defined as efforts and actions in the form of developing something (product and process) to become better or a form of developing something new and useful for users. The term innovation (innovativeness) is defined as the level (degree) of innovation made by individuals which consists of the following indicators: a. Products that are new; b. The process in the form of developing something new, c. Method is the way a person or organization produces a service or product. Bandura and Edwin (2006: 87-89) state that self-efficacy as a determinant for individual development, persistence in using the ability to deal with adversity, and emotional thinking and reactions that they experience. (Self-efficacy as a determining factor for individual development, persistence in using abilities to deal with adversity, and patterns of thought and emotional reactions they experience). Indicators of self-efficacy are: a. Magnitude. The magnitude dimension refers to the perception of the task that is considered difficult by the individual. The perception of this difficult task is influenced by the competence possessed by the individual; b. Strength. The strength dimension is related to the strength of a person's self-efficacy when facing the demands of a task or a problem. Weak self-efficacy can be easily negated by the anxious experience of facing a task. On the other hand, people who have strong beliefs will persevere in their efforts despite challenges, and c. Generality. The generality dimension refers to the level of students' beliefs and abilities in generalizing tasks and previous experiences. A person can judge himself to have self-efficacy in many activities or in certain activities. A person who can apply self-efficacy in various conditions, the higher his self-efficacy.

Conclusion

Based on the stages of quantitative research, starting from analyzing the results of data processing, statistical calculations, hypothesis testing, and discussing the results of research on Increasing Teacher Innovativeness through the Development of Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) and Empowerment (Empirical Studies Using Correlational Methods and SITOREM Analysis on School Teachers Based on the State Elementary School (SDN) in Bogor City, it can be concluded that this research has resulted in efforts to increase teacher innovation through identifying the strength of the relationship between the variables in the study, as follows: There is a very significant positive relationship between self-efficacy and teacher innovativeness with the level of strength very weak relationship ($ry1 = 0.148$). This means that the higher self-efficacy has a weak relationship with teacher innovation. Thus, strengthening self-efficacy has a weak opportunity to increase teacher innovation. There is a very significant positive relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and teacher innovation with a moderate level of relationship strength ($ry2 = 0.599$). This means that the higher the OCB, the higher the teacher's innovativeness. Thus, strengthening OCB can increase teacher innovation. There is a positive and significant relationship between Empowerment and Teacher Innovativeness with a strong level of relationship strength ($ry3 = 0.713$). This means that the higher the empowerment, the higher the teacher's innovativeness. Thus, strengthening empowerment can increase teacher innovativeness. There is a positive and significant relationship between Self-Efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior together with Teacher Innovativeness with a strong level of relationship strength ($ry12 = 0.669$). This means that the higher the Self-Efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior, the higher the Teacher's Innovativeness. Thus, strengthening Self-Efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior can increase teacher innovation.5. There is a positive and significant relationship between Self-Efficacy and Empowerment together with Teacher Innovativeness with a strong level of relationship strength ($ry13 = 0.714$). This means that the higher the Self-Efficacy and Empowerment, the higher the Innovativeness of the Teacher. Thus, strengthening Self-Efficacy and Empowerment can increase teacher innovation.6. There is a positive and significant relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment together with Teacher Innovativeness with a strong level of relationship strength ($ry23 = 0.746$). This means that the higher the Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment, the higher the Teacher's Innovativeness. Thus, strengthening Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Empowerment can increase teacher innovation.7. There is a positive and significant relationship between Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Empowerment together with Teacher Innovativeness with a strong level of relationship strength ($ry123 = 0.767$). This means that the higher the Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Empowerment, the higher the Teacher's Innovativeness. Thus, strengthening Self-Efficacy, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Empowerment can increase teacher innovativeness. In addition, the results of the SITOREM

analysis show that based on the priority order of improvement, it can be proposed to recommend indicators that need to be improved and indicators that need to be maintained.

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